

Synthesis of 2-Methoxy-6-Methyl Carbazole¹ and 6-Methyl (2':2' Dimethyl 5':6') 1:2 Pyrano-Carbazole²

D. P. Chakraborty, D. Chatterji and B. K. Chowdhury

Synthesis of title compounds have been reported

Girinimbine, $C_{18}H_{17}NO$, m.p. 176° an optically inactive carbazole derivative isolated by Chakraborty, Barman and Bose³ was partially formulated as (I). In course of our studies on the carbazoles of Rutaceae, we carried out further studies on its structure. From degradative studies, we came to the conclusion that girinimbine could be represented as (II) or (III)⁴. The structure (III)⁴ was announced which awaited synthetic confirmation. To provide such confirmation, we synthesised 2-methoxy-6-methyl carbazole (IV) to identify a methoxy carbazole, $C_{14}H_{13}NO$, m.p. 225° (V), *o*-methyl derivative of decarbonylation product of an α -hydroxy aldehyde (VI), $C_{14}H_{11}NO_2$, m.p. 193° , obtained by ozonolysis of girinimbine. Besides this, we also synthesised 6-methyl (2':2'-dimethyl 5':6') 1:2 pyrano-carbazole (VII) to identify it with dihydrogirinimbine. Both these synthetic compounds were not identical with the compounds derived from the girinimbine. This shows that the structure (II) would be more probable which has been proved by spectral⁵, synthetic^{6,7} and degradative^{6,7}, evidences.

(I)

(II) $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$

(III) $R_1 = CH_3$; $R_2 = H$

The present communication relates to the syntheses of the compounds (IV) and (VII).

- Partly from the D.Phil. thesis of B.K.C., Calcutta Univ., 1966.
- Partly from the D.Phil. thesis of D. Chatterji, Calcutta Univ., 1968.
- D. P. Chakraborty, B. K. Barman and P. K. Bose, *Sci. and Cult.*, 1964, **30**, 445.
- D. P. Chakraborty and B. K. Chowdhury, Proc. IUPAC Symp. on the Chem. Natural Products, 418, 1968.
- N. L. Dutta and C. Quasim, *Ind. J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 307.
- (a) D. P. Chakraborty, K. C. Das and B. K. Chowdhury—*J. Org. Chem.*, 1971 (in press)
 (b) A. Islam, D.Phil. thesis, Jan. 1970.
- B. S. Joshi, Paper presented at Indo Soviet Symp. of Chem. of Natural Products, Feb. 1970.

2-hydroxy methylene-5-methyl cyclohexanone (VIII) was condensed⁸ with diazotised *m*-anisidine (IX) when 4-methyl cyclohexane 1 : 2-dione-1-*m*-methoxy phenyl hydrazone (X), m.p. 186–88°, was obtained which on indolisation furnished a mixture of compound (XI) and (XII). From the compound (XI) on Wolff-Kishner reduction 2-methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole (XIII), C₁₄H₁₇NO, m.p. 134° was obtained which on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal furnished 2-methoxy-6-methyl carbazole, C₁₄H₁₃NO, m.p. 225° was obtained, the uv. spectrum of which was ($\lambda_{max}^{ethanol}$ 236, 258, 302 m μ with log ϵ 4.70, 4.32 and 4.20 respectively) characteristic for 2-methoxy carbazole chromophore.

The appropriate indole (XVI) acylated with $\beta\beta$ -dimethyl acryloyl chloride after Fries rearrangement and subsequent cyclisation would yield the chromanone required for (VIII). During Fries rearrangement the migration of the acyl function to 3-position would be much more favoured from mechanistic considerations. So we took *p*-aminosalicylic acid as the starting amino compound from which the carboxylic acid group could readily be removed. 2-Hydroxymethylene-5-methyl cyclohexanone was condensed with the diazonium chloride of the methylester of *p*-aminosalicylic acid (XIV) under Japp-Klingemann condition when 4-methyl cyclohexane-1 : 2 dione

1'-(3'-hydroxy-4'-carbomethoxy) phenyl hydrazone (XV), $C_{15}H_{18}N_2O_4$, m.p. 188–89° was obtained. The compound (XV) was indolised to 2-hydroxy 6-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole-3-carboxylate (XVI), $C_{15}H_{15}NO_4$, λ_{max} . 265 and 305 $m\mu$ with $\log \epsilon$ 4.22 and 4.23; ν_{max}^{Nujol} 3333 (–NH function), 3165 (–OH), 1642 (–CO chelated) 1616, 885 cm^{-1} (aromatic residue).

The oxo compound (XVI) was then acylated with $\beta\beta$ -dimethyl acryloyl chloride in presence of dry pyridine when the compound (XVII), $C_{20}H_{21}NO_5$, m.p. 184–85° was obtained.

The acylated compound (XVII) was subjected to Fries migration to form 2 : 1 (2' : 2'-dimethyl pyran-4'-one) 6-methyl 8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro carbazole-3-carboxylate (XVIII), $C_{20}H_{21}NO_5$, m.p. 146–47°, λ_{max} 260, 310 $m\mu$ with $\log \epsilon$ 4.29 and 3.85. The compound (XVIII) on Clemenson reduction furnished a gummy substance (XIX) soluble in aqueous bicarbonate. As the substance was gummy, it was worked up for the next step without taking recourse to purification. The compound (XIX) on decarboxylation⁹ with $SbCl_5$ furnished a colourless unstable compound (XX) insoluble in aqueous bicarbonate. The decarboxylated compound on dehydrogenation with palladised charcoal furnished the desired 2 : 2 dimethylpyrano carbazole, m.p. 170–74°. The uv. and ir. spectra of the compounds are similar to dihydrogirinimbine but there is difference in m.m.p.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methyl cyclohexane-1 : 2 dione 1-m-methoxy phenyl hydrazone (X) : To a solution of 2-hydroxymethylene-5-methyl cyclohexanone (3.5 g.) in methanol (36 ml) was added to the freshly prepared solution of diazotised *m*-anisidine (3 g.) in presence of aqueous solution (19 ml) of NaOAc (5.5 g.) throughout a period of 30 mins. The precipitate obtained was washed and crystallised from alcohol when the hydrazone, $C_{14}H_{18}N_2O_2$, m.p. 186–88° was

9. B. K. Chowdhury and D. P. Chakraborty, *Chem. and Industry*, 1969, 549.

obtained. (Found : C, 68.11; H, 7.29; N, 11.48. $C_{14}H_{18}N_2O_2$: requires C, 68.27; H, 7.37; 11.37%).

2-methoxy-6-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro carbazole (XI) : 4-methyl cyclohexane 1 : 2 dione-1-*m*-methoxy phenyl hydrazone was added to boiling glacial acetic acid (12 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (3.1 ml). The product obtained was filtered, dried and crystallised from benzene when the oxo-compound (XI¹⁰), $C_{14}H_{15}NO_2$, m.p. 211° was obtained. The homogeneity of the compound was tested by paper chromatography (R_f 0.75 in 56% alcohol and 4% acetic acid). (Found : C, 73.25; H, 6.54; N, 6.28; $C_{14}H_{15}NO_2$ requires C, 73.34; H, 6.59; N, 6.11%).

2-methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8 tetrahydrocarbazole (XIII) : The above oxocompound (0.4 g.) in ethylene glycol (5 ml) was reacted with hydrazine hydrate (99–100%; 0.4 g.) in presence of KOH (0.4 g.). It was refluxed for 3 hr. at 200° and then poured into iced water and kept overnight. On working up the reaction product the tetrahydrocarbazole, m.p. 134° was obtained. (Found : C, 77.86; H, 7.77; N, 6.70; $C_{14}H_{17}NO$: requires C, 78.10; H, 7.97; N, 6.51%).

2-methoxy-6-methyl carbazole (IV) : 2-Methoxy-6-methyl-5,6,7,8 tetrahydro carbazole (150 mg) was mixed with 10% palladised charcoal. The mixture was heated in a sealed tube at 250° in presence of trace amount of dry alcohol for 4 hrs. on a metal bath. On working up the reaction product a compound melting at 215° was obtained. It was crystallised from benzene and petroleum ether when colorless needles, m.p. 225° was obtained. (Found : C, 79.57; H, 6.24; N, 6.81%; $C_{14}H_{13}NO$ requires C, 79.49; H, 6.20; N, 6.63%).

Methyl ester of p-amino salicylic acid (XIV) : *p*-Amino salicylic acid (10 g) in dry methanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 5 hrs. in presence of conc. sulphuric acid (20 ml). The reaction mixture was worked up when crystals, m.p. 115–20° was obtained. This on recrystallisation from aqueous methanol melted at 120–21° (lit. m.p. 121°), yield, 9 g.

4-Methyl cyclohexane-1 : 2-dione 1'-(3'-hydroxy-4'-carbomethoxy) phenyl hydrazone (XV) : To a solution of 2-hydroxy methylene 5-methyl cyclohexanone (6.4 g.) in methanol (40 ml) was gradually added (45 mins) to a solution of diazotised methyl ester of *p*-amino salicylic acid in presence of aqueous solution of NaOAc (15 g.) under mechanical agitation. The ppt. was separated by means of filtration, washed with water to free it from acid and dried. The products obtained was crystallised from benzene-pet. ether mixture m.p. 188–89°. Yield 4.0 g. (Found : C, 61.89; H, 6.15; N, 9.04. $C_{14}H_{18}N_2O_4$ requires C, 62.06; H, 6.25; N, 9.15%).

*2-hydroxy-6-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole 3-carboxylate (XVI)*¹¹ : The compound (XV), (3.6 g.) was indolised with boiling glacial acetic acid (27 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (6 ml) under reflux condition (10 mins). The reaction product was poured into

10. Compounds XI and XII were separated by chromatography over silica gel.

11. Separated from its 4-methoxy isomer by Chromatography.

crushed ice (50 g.) and on working up furnished a brown oil. This was then purified by chromatography over silica gel. It was then crystallised from benzene-pet. ether (40–60°) mixture, when pale yellow needles melting at 121–22° were obtained. Yield 1.7 g. (Found : C, 65.76; H, 5.26; N, 4.98. $C_{15}H_{15}NO_4$ requires C, 65.93; H, 5.53; N, 5.13%).

Dimethyl acrylate of 2-hydroxy-6-methyl 8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro carbazole-3-carboxylate (XVII) : 2-hydroxy-6-methyl-8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrocarbazole-3-carboxylate (1.5 g.) was acylated with $\beta\beta$ -dimethyl acryloyl chloride (0.5 g.) in presence of dry pyridine (10 ml). The reaction mixture was then kept for 24 hrs at room temp. The dark coloured reaction mixture was poured into a large amount of crushed ice containing dil. HCl when a solid product was obtained. The solid was filtered, washed with dil. HCl and finally with water. After drying, the solid was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 184–85°. Yield 0.9 g.

2 : 1 (2' : 2'-dimethyl pyran-4'-one)-6-methyl 8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro carbazole-3-carboxylate (XVIII) : A mixture of dimethyl acrylate of 2-hydroxy 6-methyl 8-oxo-5,6,7,8-tetrahydro carbazole-3-carboxylate (0.85 g.) and powdered anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (4.5 g.) was dissolved in freshly distilled nitrobenzene (35 ml) at 0–5° and the mixture was kept at room temp. for 3 days. After completion of the reaction the mixture was poured into crushed ice (100 g.) and dil. hydrochloric acid (25 ml.). The product was extracted with ether and the ethereal layer was washed with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and then with water. Removal of ether and nitrobenzene by steam distillation left a resinous material. It was again extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with 1% alkali and then with water. On drying and on removal of the solvent a solid product was obtained. It was crystallised from benzene-pet. ether (40–60°) mixture, when pale yellow crystals were obtained, m.p. 146–47°. Yield 0.190 g. (Found : C, 67.33; H, 5.74; N, 3.590 : $C_{20}H_{21}NO_5$ requires C, 67.59; H, 5.96; N, 3.94%).

2 : 1 (2' : 2'-dimethyl pyrano)-6-methyl 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro carbazole-3-carboxylic acid (XIX) : A solution of the chromanone (0.17 g.) in a mixture of alcohol (25 ml.), acetic acid (5 ml.) and conc. hydrochloric acid (20 ml), containing amalgamated zinc (20 g.) was kept at room temp. for 2 days. The mixture was heated on water bath for 1 hr. and then refluxed for 16 hrs. with the addition of more acid (20 ml) and alcohol (20 ml). The cooled, filtered solution was made acid free and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the ether a gummy substance (0.1 g) was obtained. The gummy substance was soluble in 1% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution.

2 : 1 (2' : 2'-dimethyl pyrano) 6-methyl 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro carbazole (XX) : The gummy substance (0.09 g.) and antimony trichloride (2 g.) was heated on an oil-bath for 15 min. at 145–60°. The mixture was then cooled and extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed with ice cooled conc. hydrochloric acid till the solution was free from antimony. Then the ether layer was washed with water, aqueous bicarbonate and water successively. It was then dried and a very unstable colourless compound was obtained after removal of ether.

2 : 1 (2' : 2'-dimethyl pyrano) 6-methyl carbazole : Tetrahydrocarbazole (XX) was dissolved in *p*-cymene (2 ml) and 10% palladised charcoal (20 mg) was added to it in a sealed tube. The mixture was then refluxed at 200° in an oil-bath for 5 hr. After reaction, the solvent

was separated from Pd/C by filtration and *p*-cymene solvent was evaporated on a water-bath. On removal of the solvent a brownish residue mixed with a little amount of oil was obtained. The compound on chromatographic purification over alumina column, melted at 175–76° (crystallised from benzene : pet. ether).

The authors thank Prof. S. M. Sircar, Director, Bose Institute, Dr. A. Sen, Head of the Dept of Chemistry for their interest in the work. The financial supports by C.S.I.R. (to B.K.C.) and by the Ministry of Education (to D. Chatterjee) are gratefully acknowledged.

Bose Institute.
Calcutta-9

Received June 4, 1970